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HR and Psychology - Psychology in Organizational Excellence

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1. Abstract

Generation Z or Gen Z includes people born between the years 1995 and 2012; they will be entering the workforce and HR should re-examine their policies to cater to their needs. The history, economics, geopolitics, technology and parenting styles of each period have a great influence on that particular generation. The influence of social media, need for intensive working relations, wish for autonomy, space and diversity are all part of employability characteristics of Gen Z. The need for instant gratification, and work life balance are very high and hence they are less likely to stick to a job - which is a major concern for employers. Getting a realistic job preview of the living conditions and Motivational Cultural intelligence is one of the important factors influencing work adjustment. An increasingly diverse population of potential employees has influenced and affected HR processes in general and will continue to influence Gen Z; thus, an inclusive workplace that celebrates diversity can improve productivity. Biculturals (people having parents of different cultural heritage) also have a different effect in leadership. They have higher levels of Attributional Complexity and attributional knowledge which help in providing a less culturally biased HR management. We also notice a gradual change in the preference of selection, recruitment and retention of employees - many countries now want to focus on nationalisation of job opportunities. These are also some of the other factors that could affect the trends of HRM of Gen Z. This report is a literature review of past research into workplace diversity and of cross-cultural retention in Gen Y; and to determine how effective it has been in Gen Y, and the prospective application of this research on Gen Z.

2. Keywords

Generation Z, Human resource management

3. Introduction

“A generation, or a generational cohort, is a group born in the same defined period of years and have been exposed to similar societal and historical life events during critical stages of their formative development” (Schaie, 1965). Responses to social, environmental stimuli, their set of value systems tend to be similar among the members of the same generation [1]. Responses to social, environmental stimuli, the set of value systems and ways of interpreting events tend to be similar

among the members of the same generation. Work related values, reactions to authority and actions or behavior that satisfy their values also significantly vary from generation to generation. Generation Z or Post Millennials are those born after 1995 and raised during the 2000s. They are invaluable agents of change in business.

The objective of this literature review is to understand the gap between the HR practices for the inclusion of Gen Z employees from different cultures as compared to that in Gen Y, and help manage this difference in innovative ways to gain maximum productivity for the organization.

4 Main Differences

According to George Beall [2], the major differences seen in Gen Z compared to Gen Y are:

- **Less focus** - Gen Z have a lower attention span and patience than Gen Y since they constantly use faster information processing technology (Jenkins, 2015).
- **Better multi-tasking** - they are more efficient while switching between tasks and are more capable of handling background disturbances during work
- **Early workers** - contrary to Gen Y, it has been predicted that Gen Z is more likely to join work and finish schooling online; rather than the traditional method of finishing higher education first. They are more capable of learning things themselves through a more efficient or non-traditional route which are more cost-effective.
- **Influence of major events** - major events such as that of the 9/11 attacks, the great recession and the Mumbai terrorist attacks in India have affected and greatly influenced the attitudes of Gen Z which might have led to a feeling of unsettlement and insecurity among them. The great recession may have caused changes during their childhood by affecting their families financially. Even though Gen Y experienced these events during their coming of age, Gen Z were more affected by it since it has shaped their view of realism and world-view in their childhood. Hence Gen Z seek more security and stability over freedom and flexibility.
- **Entrepreneurship** - Gen Z tend to prefer more independent work environments and prefer setting up their own establishments instead of joining other ones. Gen Z, like the Gen Y are less likely to stick to a job for more than 3-5 years. Also, considering how most of them are born in the world of successful start-up which later established itself as successful corporate firms; their desire to be self-employed and be in charge of their own career is also very high. Hence retention is a challenge.
- **Higher expectations** - Gen Z, being born into a world surging with technology, they have much higher expectations from people and life in general
- **Individualistic** - most of the members of Gen Z have a digital footprint and are social.
- They seek uniqueness and individuality in everything they do they are creative and want to bring change (Jenkins, 2016).
- **Realistic** - Gen Z are more realistic about opportunities available and are willing to sharpen skills to be competent
- **Attitudes** - Gen Z tend to think, interact and relate globally but engage and focus on the local. They will not tolerate discrimination
- **Skill** - huge skill gap both technical and non-technical although there is a small super skilled elite group.

Theoretical literatures suggest that HR processes of an organisation contribute to the development of the HRD climate. Therefore, to bring about a change in HR management we should first look at how HR processes can be changed and made to adapt to this incoming generation [3].

HR managers play the role of a catalyst and they play a critical role in shaping the organisation. They need to be leaders who encourage change as an opportunity instead of approaching it as a threat [4].

5. Specific HRM Practices for Gen Z

Some advantageous HR practices in different areas that will help in the management of Gen z include:

5.1. Recruitment and selection

5.1.1. Social media as a chief source of outreach for potential employee recruitment: Since the generation was born and raised in a social networking world, each institution will have to make their presence felt in the same. Starting with their own official websites, blog, Facebook pages, etc, all play a key role in marketing the organization and attracting potential talent. Most people from Gen Z are likely to go on these and other sites, more than any other means, to know and understand the organization, its culture and potential job opportunities as well. Failing to connect well through these and others will be a set-back.

For the purposes of recruitment, sites like Linked In can connect you to some the best talents as they more likely to look for opportunities online (Rullion,2016).

5.1.2. Building a brand image and making your presence felt:

The generation did grow in a multicultural, multi-ethnic environment and are exposed to a lot of brands and MNCs. In the wake of growing nationalism across the world organizations; organizations must improve brand image and brand recognition [5]. This plays a vital role in recruitment and attraction of desired talent and build loyalty as generation Z is brand conscious. They want to emotionally and psychologically connect to their work, brand and organization. Hence there is no surprise if most prefer to build their own brands. They are more ecologically and environmentally aware and are philanthropist. Hence creating an ecologically and environment friendly image and being one can also help in creating an appealing image [6].

5.1.3. Catch them early:

On the contrary to the generation Y, generation Z is entering corporates straight from schools. Most of them have been volunteers in some event or the other and worked with different NGOs and for different social causes. Their desire to bring a positive change and to pursue their hobbies as a career is also increasing. Hence, this generation is success driven but a good number of them lack the skill-set to compete which could be both technical and non-technical skills. They tend to less educated and prefer to complete education by doing short term courses, online courses and are concerned on spending their resources or being burdened with heavy education loans as they have grown up during 2008 economic recessions and are exposed to its effects both directly and indirectly. Most of them have started jobs as early as from 16-19 ages, through internship and voluntary services. Sponsoring education based on requirement and talent of candidate is also great and may also help in retention [7].

5.2. Induction and retention

5.2.1. Mentoring: They value face to face interactions and wish to be mentored or coached.

As Gen Z comes into the workforce that already harbours Gen Y, it is also necessary for both these generations to be able to blend in together and cooperate for the betterment of the organization. The life experiences of the older generation and their learning can be harnessed and used in providing mentoring to the new employees for their development. Along with being mentored by the older, experienced

employees, the younger ones can in turn mentor them on the new technologies [8].

5.2.2. Job specification: Opportunity should be given to the new recruits to learn about the company employees, different positions within their field in the company, so that they get a chance to learn what the others do. Clear specification of roles and responsibilities will enhance productivity and retention. Allocating a system of ranks with all criteria's, testing protocols, rewards and responsibilities would prove to be important to ensure the required outcome [9].

5.2.3. Informal attire: There might be need to be liberal in terms of keeping a beard, wearing skinny jeans, work from home as this generation believes in being effective over efficient. The formal wear to work like suits and ties are changing to informal wear such as jeans and a shirt. Employees in the upcoming generations, prefer to come to work dressed casually, which is an employee centric shift [5]. An employee who is comfortable in what he/she is wearing is happier and more likely to perform better.

5.2.4. Helping in Work life balance: One cannot ignore the role of the family in retaining them as paternal and maternal leaves, child care and lactation facilities, family get togethers, allowing the parents to see and spent time in the campus upon induction all can influence retention as they are highly family oriented and want work life balance (Marchetti, 2014).

3.2.5. Communication: Forming online groups with team members, peer leader and line managers to check on activity and to commute and connect more efficiently and faster [1]. The building of a good rapport with team members and their line managers or immediate head is very important in retention as loyalty is built to them as individuals and not to the faceless organization [6]. Improving bonding between employees of all levels will enhance tolerance and acceptance of diversity.

5.3. Compensation and benefits

5.3.1. Providing creative benefits: Other than the usual pay that is similar among all age groups, Gen Z might demand more. Individuals could be given compensation and benefits tailored on the basis of employee's life stage economic and physical needs. According to Chaandrashekar & Naresh [10], companies such as Reliance Industries Limited, which have implemented some of the following benefits, have found that these innovative incentives have shown to increase motivation and retention in employees.

Education policy can create opportunities such as higher education catered to improving the relevant knowledge and skill set can be provided. Monetary help to pursue international courses, post graduate courses and professional courses along with secure job can be an option [10].

Policies can be created to purchase and subscribe to technical or non-technical books, journals, magazines and other work related resources in support of personal and competency development. Policies which provide claiming telephone, Wi-Fi expenses during employment can help the employee [10].

Provision of healthcare for the employee as well as their family member is an important factor. This may include regular check-up, insurance for few years, etc. Retired employees can get benefits tailored for their needs.

Businesses can include paying to some extent towards the employees' Gym memberships, Sport club Memberships, Counselling sessions, Sauna and massages [10]. Extended paid leave for maternity, paternity and marriage can be made available to help in the work life balance.

5.4. Training

There also exists differences in the training needs of different generations. When formal training is needed, usage of multiple methods of teaching is usually recommended to address the needs of workers, even though most of the employees prefer learning 'soft skills' on the job [11]. The common preference of workers from different generations include discussion groups, peer interaction and feedback, on the job learning, and one-on-one coaching to learn 'soft skills'. Yet, there are methods that are preferred by the members of one generation and not the other. For example, younger generation workers do not prefer classroom teaching for learning 'soft skills'; they prefer assessment and feedback to learn 'soft skills', which is not the case for the members of the older generation. HR managers should take into consideration these differences while teaching 'soft skills' [11]. Differentiating training for the learning of hard skills may not be required since both generations have similar preference. Training needs differ between both the generations and it is necessary for HR managers to understand the requirements and provide the same, instead of providing 'blanket' training for all employees [11].

5.5. Improve employee experience

The exiting workforce demands change. They require stimulation, challenges to keep them interested and motivated. Attracting the desired talented employees and maintaining their well-being in the organizational setting, will give forth much output to the company, in the long run [5].

5.5.1. Ensure workplace wellness: A dedicated staff, expenditure for increasing the happiness and health of employee is important. The employees' wellness will have a huge effect in their productivity and retention. This can be done in the form of providing meal options, sports and recreation activities, and comfortable work space. This gives them a positive motivation to want to come to work [5].

5.5.2. Flexibility of work: The work-from-home option is increasing and may soon become a major factor which prospective employee's seek. Flexible hours can be provided where only productivity is measured and given more importance to [1].

5.6. Cultural inclusion

According to Buddhapriya [12], analysis of diversity management practices in three leading IT multinational organisations of India reveal that dynamic business environment, global operation, dependence on knowledge and talent shortage are the major reasons for focusing on diversity. It is also seen that diversity of nationality and diversity of gender have received the greatest attention compared to other issues such as diversity of race, differently-abled, underprivileged, etc. The major challenge faced is to make employees develop an attitude of acceptance and accommodation towards people from different backgrounds. Employees usually fail to keep aside their cultural values, lifestyle preferences and differences at work. Attention towards diversity management initiatives have only

started during the last decade in India. Organisations have also started linking diversity with their strategic objectives. Infosys believes that to retain global talent they need to offer best diversity opportunities.

There are various reasons why companies such as WIPRO, INFOSIS, HCL have properly established diversity management practices. Being global companies and operating in different countries in the world, they have deliberately introduced a highly diverse workforce. For them to manage a diverse workforce is 'no longer a choice but imperative'. They operate in a business environment which has increased diversity among customers, clients and the employees. They operate in a highly competitive and dynamic environment and therefore acquisition and retention of talent is a challenge. Developing and sustaining a healthy mix of talent is essential. Since these companies are part of the knowledge-based sector they depend on innovation, and innovation is driven by diversity. Workforce diversity is new trend being adopted by Indian organisations. With the growing increase for diversity, organisations which want to thrive should have employees and managers who understand the importance of diversity and inclusion, and must have the necessary skills to deal with these important issues.

6. Limitations and Area of Future Research

This paper was done based on different studies done on generation-Z. Since the number already in workforce is very negligible hence the effectiveness of these strategies are yet to be tried and tested. The role of different social, economic, cultural, parenting styles needs to be studied and assessed on a national level as well. The rise in extreme nationalistic policies against expatriates and imported goods and services will have new effects which need to be assessed. The research in terms of generation Z is yet to be done. Even health disorders like obesity and ADHD are more common due to their sedentary lifestyle and constant exposure of screen. Hence, these will affect productivity and in turn affect ways to address the same in a corporate setting will change. Also, since they were born in a multicultural environment, further study needs to be done on how people with multicultural, multi-religious backgrounds, being diaspora or children of expatriates or expatriates themselves will affect them in a local and global market in line with the present geopolitical and economic changes happening throughout the world.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we have discussed some Gen Z Management Strategies that may be adopted by HR managers, which will also promote diversity acceptance and tolerance. intergenerational conflicts are also likely to affect productivity and organizational culture if left unattended and can result in huge loss. Gen Z was found to prefer to be mentored and coached hence constant reeducation for technical and soft-skills, recognition, feedback for the same is required. Having a strong presence in Social Media and improving brand image would help in the attraction and recruitment of Gen Z. To retain the elite group of employees, in both the individual and the companies interest, there must be efforts to build good work conditions, ensure wellness of employee, introduction of relevant rewards and benefits, and provision of flexible work hours. Creating an environment in which the employee can give maximum productivity is the aim. Providing constant feedback is also required for the

employee to develop continuously. Cultural diversity management is an important criterion under.

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